

Enhancing Quality And Productivity In Automated Fiber Placement: Strategies For AFP Programming, In-process Inspection and Process Optimization

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Introduction

What is AFP?:

- Automated Fiber Placement (AFP) is a manufacturing process that uses computer controlled AFP machines to make composite structures by laying down composite slit tape layer by layer precisely.

Why AFP?:

- Large structures with complex shapes
- Consistent quality
- Faster and efficient
- Less waste and cost
- High precision and quality

Manufacturing fuselage panels for the A350 XWB (Picture © Premium Aerotec GmbH.)

Composites Research at NRC Aerospace

- Composites manufacturing
 - Automated fibre placement
 - Liquid composite moulding
 - Thermoplastic composite joining and manufacturing
 - Autoclave processing
 - Compression moulding
 - Low-cost tooling
- Process modeling and simulation
- Composites joining and repair
- Structure design and stress analysis
- Material characterization and mechanical testing

Automated Fiber Placement Activities at NRC Aerospace

Tail boom

Front Fuselage

Isogrid Panel

Automated Fiber Placement Activities at NRC Aerospace

Helicopter skid

Thermoplastic tailboom

Process modelling and simulation

Key Stages in Automated Fiber Placement Process

- Part Design
- AFP Simulation and Programming
- AFP Manufacturing
- Inspection and Quality Control
- Part Curing
- Testing and Evaluation

Our strategy: Optimize the AFP process by optimizing each individual stage

The challenge: Each stage is linked to the others. Optimizing any stage depends on iterative data transfer and feedback within a closed-loop workflow

AFP Simulation

Main Tasks of AFP Simulation

- Tooling validation and process feasibility study
- Ply coverage generation and optimization
- Defects prediction, e.g. gaps/laps and fiber steering, etc.
- AFP programming and virtual commissioning
- Productivity and cost analysis

0%·Overlap → → 100%·Overlap

Important Parameters for AFP Simulation

- Mesh size
- Surface update
- Tow count and tow thickness
- Coverage method, start point and layup directions
- Fiber orientation
- Stagger offset
- Gap/overlap ratios
-

Fiber stagger

Case Study: Fiber Placement of A Curved Composite Panel

Part Info:

- Panel size: 15.5 x 27 inches
- Material: Carbon fiber/epoxy
- Layup sequence: [45/0/-45/0]s

AFP Simulation: Surface Meshing

Common question:
Is the mesh size good enough for this part?

- Finer mesh improves path accuracy on complex surface
- Mesh size depends on geometry, part size, and computer capability
- For example, for this curved panel, reducing mesh from 5 mm to 2 mm increased ply time by 2.5x

Mesh Strategy: Balancing simulation accuracy and computational time is key

AFP Simulation: Tooling Validation and Process Feasibility Study

Collision in 0° ply

Collision in 45° ply

AFP Simulation: Identifying potential collisions (*illustrative example, not from this project*)

AFP Simulation: Coverage Method Selection

Parallel Limited (3° dev. allowed)

Natural Path

Fixed Angle

Fixed Parallel

Coverage Method Selection Strategies:

- Design requirements
- Part geometry
- Part application

AFP Simulation: Influence of Start Point Location

Start Point:

- The start point acts as the origin for coverage generation
- It is one of the most critical parameters in AFP simulation

AFP Simulation: Influence of Start Point Location

A proprietary program developed at NRC, *AFP Simulation Summary*, was used to analyze AFP simulation data

AFP Simulation Summary

AFP Programming Parameters	Summaries	Notes
ACE V2 Version	V2.R2.72n (Coverage); V2.R2.72o (Program)	
Project Description	Influence of start point	Project #: TBD
Date of Documentation (Y/M/D)	2025-06-25	
AFP Part Name	StartPoint: Middle	
ACE Program Name	CurvedTool_Fiber Path Analysis	
Ply Number #	Ply 0005	BDY Name: Boundary_EXT
Path Orientation (ACE Axis System)	45	FAD <= 3°: 100.00 (%); FAD <= 5°: 100.00 (%)
Average Tool Misalignment (in)	0.03386	Tool misalignment is moderate
Ply Layup on Surface #	5	
Tow Count	32	
Course Count in this Ply	9	
Coverage Method	Fixed Parallel	
Coverage Start Point (Design Coordinate)	X=3.491, Y=1.19, Z=4.445	
Coverage Step Size (in)	0.25	
Gap in the Ply %	0	
Overlap in the Ply %	0	
Min Ply Roller Sag (in)	-0.028	
Max Ply Roller Crown (in)	0.257	No compaction issues expected
Minimum Tow Length Used for the Ply Coverage (in)	0.00	Warning: Patches are needed for short fiber paths
The Ply's Minimum Radius of Curvature (in)	27.37	Warning: Medium risk of fiber wrinkles
Head Clearance DistanceX (in)	40.00	
Collision Avoidance Enable	TRUE	
Predicted Material Usage of the Ply (lb)	0.132	
Predicted Ply Cycle Time (h:m:s) [On Surface]	00:01:59 [00:00:48]	
Predicted Material Yield (lbs/hour)	3.979	AFP down time is not included in the calculation

* The warnings in this table are based on AFP simulation results. The final results of AFP process will be also influenced by various other manufacturing parameters

This Table is generated by the AFP Simulation Summary program

AFP Manufacturing: Parameters and Strategies

Important Parameters for AFP Manufacturing

- Compaction force
- Fiber tension
- Heating temperature
- Humidity level
- Layup speed
- Material tackiness
- Substrate temperature
-

Strategies to Improve AFP Productivity and Quality

- Establish standard work instructions for AFP setup and operation
- Use virtual simulation to pre-validate layup strategy
- Perform dry-run of the AFP program - fully or only in critical areas for large parts
- Maximize layup speed
- Use large material spools to reduce load time
- Enable automated in-line inspection to reduce downtime
- Adjust parameters based on material & environment conditions
- Avoid small cutouts, tight radii, and complex geometries in design
- Favor long continuous fiber courses during path planning
- Optimize layup sequence and fiber direction
- Minimize off-surface movements of the AFP head
- Schedule regular head maintenance — don't wait for failure

AFP Manufacturing: Data Tracking and Analysis

AFP-Layup-Information¶

Total-number-of-plyes-for-this-part:-14-plyes¶
 AFP-Machine-Time-(min):-22.07¶
 Down-Time-(min):-173.00¶
 Total-Time-(min):-195.07¶
 Machine-Occupation-Time-(min):-3-hours-and-16.48-minutes¶
 Fibers-Length-(in):-33943.41¶
 Fiber-Delivery-(in/min):-1424.85¶
 Weight-(lbs):-1.35¶
 Wasted-Material-(lbs):-0.17¶
 Layup-Rate-(lbs/hr):-3.41¶

Error-Messages¶

Tensioner-Fault:-4¶
 Problem-While-Restarting:-3¶
 Problem-While-Feeding:-2¶
 Zp-Axis-Fault:-0¶
 Pressure-Fault:-0¶
 Bladder-failure:-0¶
 Other-Errors:-0¶
 Total-Errors:-9¶

A proprietary program developed at NRC, *AFP Process Analysis*, was used to analyse AFP manufacturing process

Quality Assurance

Typical AFP Manufacturing Defects

- Gaps/overlaps
- Fiber bridging
- Wrinkles
- Fiber fuzz
- Missing tow
- Twisted tow
- Foreign Object/debris (FOD)

In-Process Inspection

- Conducts real-time inspection
- Operates without interfering with the AFP process
- Identifies the type, dimensions and location of the defects
- Provides warnings for the oversized defects that need rework
- Documents the inspection results automatically
- Creates digital data tracking and travelers
- Largely increases the efficiency of the AFP process

- Patented technology based on **Optical Coherence Tomography technology**—a mature laser-based, volumetric imaging technique

- Process driven custom sensor system designed and integrated with various AFP machines in partnership with Fives Group

NRC's Viper 4000:

NRC prototype sensor

Fives Robotic Viper:

Fives COAST system

In-Process Inspection

More info about Fives COAST system: <https://youtu.be/L2Q9SvEcAfc?si=NhkV8qsMtZ6iQv69>

In-Line Inspection System: Examples of Defect Detection

In-process measurements:

High resolution 3D located point cloud

Ply 60, approx. 9.7 mm thick ply stack

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Summary

- AFP process can be categorized into six key stages: CAD design, AFP simulation and programming, AFP manufacturing, inspection and quality control, part curing, testing and evaluation
- Closed-loop data flow is essential in AFP process — each AFP stage influences and depends on the others
- AFP process optimization relies on continuous feedback between stages to ensure better outcome
- NRC is actively developing software tools and sensors to collect, track, and analyze AFP simulation and process data
- These capabilities have enabled NRC to successfully develop hundreds of composite structures with partners across sectors
- We will continue refining this approach — using ply-by-ply AFP simulation studies to guide design decisions and ensure consistent, high-quality outcomes

Thank You

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